

Original Article:

Incidence, clinical presentation, relapses and outcome of SARS-CoV-2 infection in patients treated with anti-CD20 monoclonal antibodies

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Keywords: Rituximab, antiCD20 monoclonal antibodies, COVID-19, SARS-CoV2 infection, COVID-19 relapse.

Manuscript counts:

Key Points word count: 42

Abstract word count: 252

Manuscript word count: 3000

Tables: 5

Figures: 1

Key Points:

This retrospective cohort study of 422 patients under antiCD20 treatment was not associated with an increased risk of SARS-CoV-2 infection, but if infected during the 6 months after the treatment, had higher hospital admission, mortality, longer infectivity and relapses of COVID-19.

ABSTRACT

Background:

Our objective is to describe the presentation and complications, including relapses, of COVID-19 in patients under anti-CD20 treatments. Also, to describe viral clearance and determine the safety of reintroducing anti-CD20 treatment.

Methods:

Retrospective cohort study of 422 patients under anti-CD20 treatment administered from January 1, 2019, to December 31, 2020.

Results.

Fifty-seven patients were diagnosed of COVID-19 (13.5%). 25 patients (43.9%) required hospital admission. 5 patients died (8.8%), 10 developed critical COVID-19 and acute respiratory distress syndrome. Mortality rate was higher among patients infected during the first 3 months following the last dose of anti-CD20 (14.7% vs 0%, $p=0,046$).

The median time of persistence of positive RT-PCR was 22 days (IQR 13-40).

Nine out of 52 survivors (17.3%) presented relapses. All of them received the last dose of anti-CD20 more than 6 months before the COVID-19 episode. Clinical presentation was fever ($n=8$; 88.9%), dyspnea ($n=7$; 77.8%), cough ($n=7$; 77.8%), worsening of previous infiltrates ($n=5$; 55.6%) and new pulmonary infiltrates ($n=8$; 88.9%). An increase in lymphocytes with CD4/CD8 ratio inversion was observed in all cases.

Among the 25 patients in whom anti-CD20 drug was restarted, 4 (16.0%) presented relapses vs 5/28 in whom it was not restarted (17.9%), ($p=0.857$).

Conclusion:

Patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 during the 6 months after anti-CD20 administration have worse outcome and higher mortality rate. The duration of infectivity may be longer.

Relapses of COVID-19 occur in more than 15% and are associated with viral replication.

Once the infection is resolved, it is safe to restart treatment with anti-CD20.

INTRODUCTION

A subset of COVID-19 patients develop an exaggerated inflammatory response by innate immunity, responsible for acute respiratory distress(1–3). The humoral immune response and production of neutralizing antibodies by B-lymphocytes are essential in viral clearance (4,5), and would be able to reduce the inflammatory damage.(1,4,6)

During the last two decades, monoclonal anti-CD20 antibodies have been available for treatment of different diseases. These antibodies act selectively on B-lymphocytes and decrease antibody production.(7–9) This could lead to a depressed humoral response (5,10,11). It is biologically plausible that these patients may have inability in virus clearance, and this could induce an increased inflammation. Hence, patients treated with these drugs could have higher risk of severe COVID-19 and death (12–14). Case reports of atypical presentation, persistence of viral replication, protracted symptomatology, and relapses have been reported (15,16). These patients could benefit from specific therapeutic approach, including transfusion of convalescent plasma, to counterbalance the absence of production of antibodies (16). Despite these findings, there is no published series of patients treated with anti-CD20 to describe COVID-19 in this population. neither have been identified risk factors for severe infection, death and relapses.

Our primary objectives were to describe the incidence, clinical presentation and complications (including relapses) of COVID-19 in patients under anti-CD20 treatments. We aimed to identify those patients at risk of severe infection or death. Our secondary objectives were to describe the immune response and infectivity in these patients, and to determine the safety of reintroducing anti-CD20 treatment once the infection was overcome.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

A retrospective observational study was performed from February 2020 to March 2021 in a tertiary teaching hospital.

We retrospectively reviewed the electronic medical history of all patients aged 18 years or older treated with any anti-CD20 drug from January 1, 2019, through December 31, 2020. All patients with confirmed COVID-19 after at least one dose of anti-CD20 treatment were included. Patients were followed-up until April 30th, 2021, or death.

Antigenic rapid tests were performed by Panbio COVID-19 Ag Rapid Test Device (Abbott®, US) that uses human IgG specific to SARS-CoV-2. Serological tests were performed by chemiluminescence immunoassay method: Liaison®XL (DiaSorin) that detects IgG anti-S1/S2 and IgM specific antibodies to SARS-CoV-2. For reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) several automatized or semiautomatic systems were employed, such as Cobas® SARS-CoV-2 System (Roche Diagnostics), that uses target-specific forward and reverse primers for ORF1 a/b non-structural region that is unique to SARS-CoV-2 and a conserved region in the structural protein envelope E-gene, or Lightmix® Modular SARS-CoV-2 (Roche Diagnostics) where only E-gene is detected. Some of these systems reported the cycle threshold (Ct), which refers to the number of cycles of an RT-PCR required to amplify RNA until detection. A Ct less than 30 was considered infectious (17,18).

Definition and variables

Any patient with a positive viral test, including antigenic test and RT-PCR, was considered to have a confirmed COVID-19. Due to healthcare system overload and a

special high incidence of infection in March and April 2020, microbiological test could not be performed on outpatients settings, and diagnosis of such patients was based on clinical and radiological compatible findings. Thus, we also considered these patients as confirmed COVID-19

From patient`s electronic medical records, we collected data on baseline characteristics, anti-CD20 treatment, clinical, microbiological, complications and prognosis variables.

A recurrence was defined as a clinical episode of symptoms compatible with acute COVID-19, accompanied by re-positive/persisting RT-PCR in respiratory samples. According to previously published definitions (19), a relapse was defined as a clinical recurrence occurring within 90 days of primary infection and supported by the absence of epidemiological exposure. A reinfection was considered as a clinical recurrence occurring more than 90 days after the initial episode and with an epidemiological exposure. Since in patients under anti-CD20 treatment, there have been described confirmed relapses with the same strain more than 90 days after the initial episode without new epidemiological exposure(20), we included these patients as possible relapses. We described as a possible relapse a consistent episode with no alternative etiology without a microbiological test of SARS-CoV-2 infection or with test with inconclusive results.

Severity of disease were defined per the NIH criteria (21).

Statistical analysis

Data are presented as median and interquartile range (IQR) for quantitative variables and as percentage and absolute value for qualitative variables. Inferential analysis was

performed using chi-square test (or Fisher exact test when necessary) for qualitative variables and Mann-Whitney's U for quantitative variables. Bilateral p-values of less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 25 software package (SPSS Inc., IBM, Chicago, Illinois, United States)

RESULTS

During the study period, 422 patients received anti-CD20 treatment. Of these, 67 patients were diagnosed COVID-19, but only 57 patients after starting anti-CD20 treatment (13.5%). Figure 1 shows the flowchart of patients.

Baseline characteristics, anti-CD20 therapy and clinical presentation are shown in Table 1. Among the 57 patients, 17 (29.8%) were under concomitant treatment with corticosteroids, 10 patients (17.5%) under another immunosuppressive treatment (4 under R-CHOP protocol, 2 under tacrolimus, and one case under each of the following: mycophenolate, azathioprine, methotrexate and belimumab).

Risk factors for severe COVID-19

Twenty-five patients (43.9%) required hospital admission due to COVID-19. All of them fulfilled NIH criteria for severe disease. Table 1 compares characteristics of severe vs non-severe patients. There were no differences in concomitant treatment with corticosteroids or other immunosuppressant therapies prior to COVID-19. Patients who were diagnosed of COVID-19 during the 6 months after the last dose of anti-CD20 developed severe disease more frequently (48.9% vs 18.0%, $p=0.090$).

Complications and outcomes

Five patients (8.8%) died. All deceased patients died during hospital admission (20% of admitted patients) and the cause of death was SARS-CoV-2 related pulmonary injury. During admission, 10 (37.5%) developed critical COVID-19, 8 (36.4%) bacterial pneumonia, 4 (13.6%) pulmonary thromboembolism. Heart failure, acute renal failure, and bacteremia occurred in 3 patients each (12.0%).

Treatment with corticosteroids was indicated in 24 (41.3%), 21 of whom were inpatients (84.0% of admitted patients). Tocilizumab was administered in 12 (48.0%). Three patients were treated with convalescent plasma. No patient received remdesivir. No significant differences in mortality were found between treatments.

Table 2 summarizes factors associated with mortality. Concomitant treatment with corticosteroids or other immunosuppressant was not associated with mortality ($p=1.000$ in both cases). None of the patients who develop COVID-19 after 6 months since last infusion died vs 10.8% of those who acquired COVID-19 within 6 months of infusion ($p=0.035$).

Time of RT-PCR positivity and immunity

Among the 19 patients with more than one RT-PCR determination, the median duration of positivity was 22 days (IQR 13-40), with a maximum of 65 days. Six patients had positive RT-PCR for more than 30 days. Three of these presented a Ct suggestive of infectivity (day 43 Ct 26, day 52 Ct 23, day 56 Ct 28), 1 unlikely infectivity (day 35 Ct 34). Persistence of positive RT-PCR for more than 30 days was associated with mortality (33.3% (2/6) vs 0% (0/13), $p=0.043$). Only 1 out of the 6 (16.7%) with RT-PCR persistently positive was under chronic corticosteroids ($p=1.000$).

Antibodies were detected in 6 out of 28 patients who had a serology determination (20.7%). The presence of serum antibodies was more likely if the episode of COVID occurred 6 months after the last anti-CD20 dose as compared to before 3 months (40.0% vs 14.2%, $p=0.072$). Three of the 6 patients with positive serology were on chronic

corticosteroid treatment (50.0%) and 2 (33.3%) on other immunosuppressant treatment ($p=0.448$ and $p=0.440$ respectively). None of the patients with positive serology presented relapses, compared to 9 out of the 22 (40.9%) with negative serology ($p=0.071$).

Time since last anti-CD20 dose

The median interval between the last dose and COVID-19 was 2 months (IQR 0.8-4.1). 35 out of 57 patients (61.4%) had SARS-CoV-2 infection within 3 months of the last dose, 11 (19.3%) between 3 and 6 months, and 11 (19.3%) after 6 months.

Clinical characteristics and outcomes of the patients according to time of the last dose of anti-CD20 drug are shown in table 3. There was a trend to more acute respiratory distress, and higher mortality among patients infected during the first 3 months (23.5% vs 8.7%, $p=0.104$, and 14.7% vs 0%, $p=0.046$, respectively).

Use of antiCD20 treatment after recovery

Thirty-five patients received an anti-CD20 drug after the episode of COVID-19, of whom 10 started on this treatment after COVID-19 recovery.

One out of the 35 patients died after receiving antiCD20 (rituximab), not being related to rituximab (related to refractory status epilepticus).

Out of the 10 patients in whom anti-CD20 was started *de novo* after COVID-19, none presented recurrences. Within the 25 patients in whom anti-CD20 drug was restarted after COVID-19, 4 (16.0%) presented recurrences vs 5 out of the 28 who did not restart treatment (17.9%), with no significant differences ($p=0.857$)

Recurrences

Out of 52 survivors of the first COVID-19 episode, 9 patients (17.3%) presented recurrences.

Table 4 shows risk factors for relapses. No recurrence occurred in patients who received the last dose of anti-CD20 more than 6 months before COVID-19. Patients with fever and dyspnea in the first episode presented recurrence more often (100% vs 59.5%, $p=0.021$; and 77.8% vs 53.8%, $p=0.019$, respectively). Chronic treatment with corticosteroids or other immunosuppressant was not associated with recurrence ($p=0.705$ and $p=0.183$ respectively).

Clinical data, treatment and evolution of relapses are summarized in table 5 at patient-level data. The time from initial diagnosis to the appearance of the first recurrence was 51 days (IQR 40-56 days), with a minimum of 36 and a maximum of 105. Four patients had more than one episode (2, 3, 5, and 6 each).

In 6 patients recurrences were classified as relapses due to microbiological confirmation within 90 days from the first episodes, 2 cases by RT-PCR in nasopharyngeal exudate, 3 by RT-PCR in bronchoalveolar lavage and one case by positive immunohistochemistry of protein-S in pneumocytes in a surgical lung biopsy. Three recurrences were classified as possible relapses (table 5): a patient with no evidence of alternative cause but without diagnostic test for SARS-CoV-2 performed (patient 4); a patient with first clinical recurrence 105 day after the initial episode, microbiologically confirmed with RT-PCR in nasopharyngeal exudate (Ct 21) and without new epidemiological exposure (patient 6);

and a patient with a RT-PCR in nasopharyngeal exudate with Ct 35, presenting symptoms consistent with viral infection and radiological worsening, without alternative cause (patient 9). We did not identify any case of suspected reinfection.

Eight patients (88.9%) presented fever, 7 (77.8%) dyspnea, 7 (77.8%) cough. 5 patients (55.6%) showed worsening of previous infiltrates, and 8 patients (88.9%) appearance of new ones. The 4 cases in which lymphocyte populations on broncoalveolar lavage was available, showed an increase in lymphocytes with CD4/CD8 ratio inversion. One episode of relapse was complicated with acute respiratory distress, 1 with pulmonary thromboembolism and 1 with superinfection (*Pneumocystis jirovecii*). There was no further complications or deaths.

DISCUSSION

Our results show that patients treated with anti-CD20 monoclonal antibodies have a higher rate of severe COVID-19 and death, a more protracted clinical course than general population, and frequent occurrence of recurrences.

These patients do not have an increased risk of SARS-CoV-2 infection compared to the general population. We identified 13.5% of patients under anti-CD20 treatment to have a diagnosis of COVID-19, whereas the last prevalence study available in our setting showed 13.2% in the general population (22).

However, these patients are at high risk of poor clinical outcome, as described by other author previously (14). Nearly half of our patients required admission, with one out of five presenting acute respiratory distress and nearly 10% mortality. Hospitalization rate were higher than general population in our setting (43.9% vs 14.7%) (23). Mortality rate was higher than what is registered worldwide (8.8% vs 2.1%) or in our country (8.8% vs 2.6%) for general population (24). For hospitalized patients, mortality was higher than previously described in our institution for general population (20.0% vs 13.8%) (25,26) and critical illness was higher than what is described in a nationwide register (37.9% vs 17.8%) (27). We also found a higher percentage of bacterial superinfections (36.4% vs 11.1%) (27). Mortality rate was also higher compared to other immunosuppressed patients described in a similar scenario than ours (20.0% vs 11.5%) (28,29). Of interest, the severity of COVID-19 was not influenced by other immunosuppressant treatments. Our data suggests the importance of the interval between the last dose of anti-CD20 drug and the diagnosis of COVID-19 in the probability of developing severe disease and death, which has been previously speculated (11) and related to the pharmacokinetics of the

anti-CD20 treatment. Rituximab is detectable in serum during 3 to 6 months and B-cell function recovers after 6 months (30,31). This would produce a deeper humoral immunosuppression in the first 6 months, especially in the first 3 months after its administration (7,30). In fact, in our study, patients who acquired COVID-19 after 6 months from last infusion have a prognosis like the general population (hospitalization 18.0% vs 14.7% (23) and mortality 0% vs 2.6%) (24). They had a higher prevalence of positive serum antibodies than patients who acquired COVID-19 in the first 6 months (40.0% vs 14.3%). We propose that patients with SARS-CoV-2 infection during the first 6 months since the last anti-CD20 dose, and particularly, in those during the first 3 months, may require additional therapeutic interventions to avert their potentially worse COVID-19 prognosis (16,32–35); however, the efficacy of such interventions in this population will require further study.

We demonstrated that a significant percentage of patients persist with positive RT-PCR months after infection, which was observed in small case reports previously (20). The positivity of these test, frequently with low Ct values, along with negative serology, suggest that these patients represent a persistent infectious focus for a longer time. Accordingly, isolation period should be longer and probably based on the negativity of RT-PCR (35).

A striking fact of our work is the high percentage of patients presenting clinical recurrence of the viral infection compared to general population, and specifically of relapses (17.3% vs 0.1%) (36). Although re-positivity may be a common phenomenon (37), clinical episodes of relapses have been previously described just sporadically (32,38–40). One out of five of our patients presented at least one episode of clinical relapse, occurring the

most of them during the next 3 months after the initial infection. In our series, risk factors for relapses include developing COVID-19 during the first months since last anti-CD20 infusion, and presenting an initial infection with more serious symptoms. Chronic corticoid or concomitant immunosuppressant drugs are not associated with relapse. The usual clinical presentation and possible complications of the relapse is consistent with acute COVID-19. A common feature in bronchoalveolar lavage is the increase in lymphocyte count, with CD4/CD8 ratio inversion. It is important to suspect a relapse of SARS-CoV-2 infection in patients with these features and its diagnosis should be pursued, including repeated RT-PCR in lower airway tract and, in cases with no other etiology, a lung biopsy with immunohistochemistry techniques. Treatment of these episodes could include the use of hyperimmune plasma and/or antiviral drugs (16,32,33).

Another controversial consideration regarding these patients is how we should manage immunosuppression once the infection has resolved (11,41–44). Our data suggests that, in patients who have recovered from COVID-19, it is safe to resume anti-CD20 therapy. Likewise, it is safe to initiate *de novo* an anti-CD20 drug in patients recovered of SARS-CoV-2 infection. Therefore, we recommend continuing or initiating anti-CD20 treatment once the symptoms have ceased and RT-PCR determinations are negative.

Although our study does not provide specific information about serologic response to SARS-CoV-2 vaccination, we did observe a higher serologic response to infection the more distant it is from the last dose. Thus, we speculate that the COVID-19 vaccine may be more effective the further it is separated from the last dose, at least 3 months, in line with what other authors have suggested (44,45). The optimal approach to vaccination requires clinical studies in this subgroup of patients.

Our study has several limitations. First, it is a retrospective unicentric study. Second, since we did not have a control group, comparisons with the general and immunocompromised population are based in data from other studies. These comparisons carry two possible biases: first, they were made without statistical tools to confirm whether the numerical difference is statistically significant; second, characteristics and comorbidities of general and immunocompromised populations may differ to our study population. However, this bias is reduced choosing population-based studies made in our medium. Third, regarding the need to prolong the isolation of these patients, we could not perform viral cultures, so we cannot ensure their infectivity. Despite this, the frequently low Ct found in our patients has been associated in previous studies with high probability of infectivity (17,18,46), providing validation to our conclusions. Fourth, we did not have access to whole-genomic analysis to confirm that recurrent episodes were caused by the same strain than the first one. However, due previously published experience (12,31,40) and the clinical profile of our patients, we hypothesized that the majority of recurrence episodes in these patients, in the absence of a new epidemiological exposure, are due to relapses. Finally, the relatively low number of patients and the observational nature of the study prevents us from drawing causal conclusions regarding treatment. Nevertheless, we believe that the data we obtained is valuable and may lead hypotheses for future therapeutic trials.

CONCLUSIONS

SARS-CoV-2 infection in patients under treatment with anti-CD20 antibodies shows an incidence like the general population, although with higher rates of hospital admission and mortality, being the risk the higher the closer in time the infection is to the last dose of anti-CD20, mainly in the first 3 months. The duration of infectivity may be longer than

in other groups. Relapses of COVID-19 occur in patients infected during the six months after anti-CD20 infusion. The use of convalescent plasma may be an option. Once the infection is resolved, it is safe to restart treatment with anti-CD20. Further studies are needed to evaluate the management of SARS-CoV-2 infection in patients treated with these drugs.

Potential conflicts of interest.

All the authors declare no conflict of interest.

Role of funding source.

No funding was received for this article.

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Figure and Tables

Figure 1: Patient's flowchart

Variable	Total (n=57)	Severe-critical COVID-19 (n=25)	Mild-moderate COVID-19 (n=32)	p	Missing	
Demographic and comorbidity						
Age	51 (41-60)	56 (42-69)	46 (40-53)	0.026	0	
Gender (female)	70.2% (40)	64.0% (16)	75.0% (24)	0.397	0	
Charlson Index	2 (1-3)	3 (1-5)	1 (0-3)	0.026	0	
Arterial hypertension	22.8 (13)	36.0% (9)	12.5% (4)	0.036	0	
Dyslipidemia	17.5% (10)	28.0% (7)	9.4% (3)	0.087	0	
Diabetes mellitus	10.5% (6)	16.0% (4)	6.3% (2)	0.388	0	
Cardiac failure	8.8% (5)	12.0% (3)	6.3% (2)	0.645	0	
Ischemic heart disease	1.8% (1)	4.0% (1)	0	-	0	
COPD	1.8% (1)	1.7% (1)	0	-	0	
Liver cirrhosis	3.5% (2)	4.0% (1)	3.1% (1)	1.000	0	
Chronic renal failure	15.8% (8)	20.0% (5)	12.5% (4)	0.485	0	
antiCD20 therapy						
Drug	Rituximab	77.2% (44)	84.0% (21)	71.9% (23)	0.149	0
	Ocrelizumab	21.1% (12)	12.0% (3)	28.1% (9)		
	Obinutuzumab	1.7% (1)	4.0% (1)	0		
Indication	Hematological malignancy	21.1% (12)	32.0% (8)	12.5% (4)	0.337	0
	Neurological	33.3% (19)	32.0% (8)	34.3% (11)		
	Systemic	42.1% (24)	32.0% (8)	50.0% (16)		
	Hematological	3.5% (2)	4.0% (1)	3.1% (1)		
AntiCD20 duration (months)	11 (0.7-27)	8.6 (2-23)	12.7 (0.5-31)	0.792	0	
Chronic corticosteroids	29.8% (17)	24.0% (6)	34.4% (11)	0.561	0	
Other immunosuppressant	17.5% (10)	16.0% (4)	18.8% (6)	0.786		
Group	< 6 months	80.7% (46)	92.0% (23)	71.8% (23)	0.090	0
	> 6 months	19.3% (11)	8.0% (2)	28.1% (9)		
PostCOVID antiCD20 dose	43.1% (25)	30.0% (6)	59.4% (19)	0.016	5	
Clinical presentation and outcomes						
Cough	70.2% (40)	79.2% (19)	67.7% (21)	0.380	2	
Expectoration	14.5% (8)	12.5% (3)	13.3% (4)	1.000	3	
Fever	67.3% (37)	95.8% (23)	45.2% (14)	0.001	2	
Thoracic pain	13.2% (7)	16.7% (4)	10.3% (3)	0.688	4	
Anosmia	29.2% (14)	30.0% (6)	28.6% (8)	1.000	9	
Asthenia	61.2% (30)	76.2% (16)	50.0% (14)	0.081	8	
Arthromyalgia	40.4% (21)	47.8% (11)	34.5% (10)	0.400	5	
Dyspnea	34.5% (19)	62.5% (15)	12.9% (4)	0.001	2	
Asymptomatic	8.6% (5)	0	8.8% (5)	-	9	
Pulmonary infiltrate	70.0% (28)	95.8% (23)	31.3% (5)	0.001	17	
COVID-related death	8.8% (5)	20.0% (20)	0	0.013	0	
Relapse	15.8% (9)	30.0% (6)	9.4% (3)	0.105	5	

Table 1: Comorbidity, antiCD20 therapy and clinical presentation of COVID-19 in patients treated with anti-CD20 drug. Chronic corticosteroids: a systemic chronic therapy with corticoids at least with 5mg/kg of prednisone or equivalent at time of SARS-CoV2 infection. COPD: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease

Variable		Total (n=57)	Survivor (n=52)	Non-survivor (n=5)	p	Missing
Demographic and comorbidity						
Age		51 (41-60)	47 (40-60)	71 (60-84)	0.001	0
Gender (female)		70.2% (40)	73.1% (38)	40.0% (2)	0.151	0
Charlson Index		2 (1-3)	2 (1-3)	5 (3-9)	0.001	0
Arterial hypertension		22.8% (13)	15.4% (8)	100% (5)	0.001	0
Diabetes mellitus		10.5% (6)	9.6% (5)	20.0% (1)	0.458	0
Cardiac failure		8.8% (5)	5.8% (3)	40.0% (2)	0.056	0
Chronic renal failure		15.8% (9)	13.5% (7)	40.0% (2)	0.173	0
AntiCD20 therapy						
Indication	Hematological Malignancy	21.1% (12)	17.3% (9)	60.0% (3)	0.082	0
	Neurological	33.3% (19)	36.5% (19)	0		
	Systemic	42.1% (24)	42.3% (22)	40.0% (2)		
	Hematological	3.5% (2)	3.8% (2)	0		
AntiCD20 duration (months)		11 (0.7-26)	12 (0.5-30)	7 (3-9)	0.274	0
Chronic corticosteroids		29.8% (17)	30.8% (16)	20.0% (1)	1.000	0
Other immunosuppressant		17.5% (10)	17.3% (9)	20.0% (1)	1.000	0
Clinical presentation						
Cough		72.7% (40)	72.0% (36)	80.0% (4)	1.000	2
Fever		67.3% (37)	64.0% (32)	100% (5)	0.102	2
Asthenia		61.2% (30)	60.0% (27)	75.0% (5)	0.649	4
Arthromyalgia		39.6% (21)	39.6% (19)	40.0% (2)	1.000	5
Dyspnea		34.5% (19)	32.0% (16)	60.0% (3)	0.209	2
Pulmonary infiltrate		70.0% (41)	65.7% (23)	100% (5)	0.118	17
LDH (UI/mL)		292 (262-411)	286 (261-398)	377 (247-675)	0.611	32
CRP (mg/L)		76 (36-152)	75 (19-145)	106 (52-199)	0.667	32
Lymphocytes (cel x10 ³ /mL)		0.7 (0.5-1.2)	0.8 (0.6-1.3)	0.4 (0.1-0.6)	0.042	32
D-Dimer(ng/mL)		855 (392-2200)	745 (315-4375)	990 (705-1495)	0.505	32
Ferritin (ng/mL)		528 (214-1646)	458 (142-1343)	1208 (473-2217)	0.357	32
Complications						
Acute respiratory distress		17.9% (10)	9.8% (5)	100% (5)	0.001	1
Bacterial pneumonia		15.1% (8)	10.2% (5)	75.0% (3)	0.009	4

Table 2: Factors associated with mortality in COVID-19 patients with previous treatment with anti-CD20. Chronic corticosteroids: a systemic chronic therapy with corticoids at least with 5mg/kg of prednisone or equivalent at time of SARS-CoV2 infection. Bacterial pneumonia: a microbiological confirmed bacterial co-infection or super-infection during the COVID-19 episode. LDH: Lactate dehydrogenase. CRP: C- reactive protein.

Variable	Total (n=57)	< 3 months (n=35)	3-6 months (n=11)	> 6 months (n=11)	p	Missing
Demographic and comorbidity						
Age	51 (41-60)	52 (44-61)	40 (30-57)	49 (30-69)	0.247	0
Gender (female)	70.2% (40)	62.9% (22)	63.6% (7)	100%	0.101	0
Charlson Index	2 (1-3)	2 (1-3)	1 (0-3)	3 (1-4)	0.264	
Clinical presentation						
Cough	72.7% (40)	66.7% (22)	100%	63.6% (7)	0.111	2
Fever	67.3% (37)	63.6% (21)	90.9% (10)	54.5% (6)	0.175	2
Asthenia	61.2% (30)	63.3% (19)	88.9% (8)	30.0% (3)	0.038	8
Arthromyalgia	40.4% (21)	35.5% (11)	60.0% (6)	36.4% (4)	0.451	6
Dyspnea	34.5% (19)	39.4% (13)	36.4% (4)	18.2% (2)	0.436	3
Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.76 (0.50-0.90)	0.73 (0.49-1.22)	0.97 (0.40-1.83)	*	0.532	32
LDH (UI/mL)	299 (263-402)	264 (246-267)	332 (138-431)	*	0.825	32
CRP (mg/L)	58 (48-152)	55 (17-83)	58 (41-103)	*	0.675	32
Lymphocytes (cel x10 ³ /mL)	0.70 (0.41-1.20)	0.41 (0.32-0.96)	0.66 (0.36-1.21)	*	0.320	32
D-Dimer(ng/mL)	910 (400-1600)	920 (445-1011)	1140 (265-2125)	*	0.437	32
Ferritin (ng/mL)	287 (186-842)	313 (184-740)	279 (179-971)	*	0.547	32
IL-6 (UI/mL)	31.7 (9.7-258)	21.6 (8.8-163)	32.7 (21-553)	*	0.330	32
Pulmonary infiltrate	70.0% (28)	66.7% (16)	70.0% (7)	83.3% (5)	0.888	18
Complications and outcomes						
Acute respiratory distress	17.9% (10)	23.5% (8)	9.1% (1)	9.1% (1)	0.094	0
Bacterial pneumonia	15.1% (8)	21.2% (7)	9.1% (1)	0	0.063	0
COVID-related death	8.8% (5)	14.3% (5)	0	0	0.035	0

*Median and IQR of blood determinations for patients with COVID-19 more than 6 months after antiCD20 are not calculable since there are only two determinations available.

Table 3: Demographic, clinical presentation, and complications of COVID-19 according to time from last infusion to infection diagnoses.

Chronic corticosteroids: a systemic chronic therapy with corticoids at least with 5mg/kg of prednisone or equivalent at time of SARS-CoV2 infection. Bacterial pneumonia: a microbiological confirmed bacterial co-infection or super-infection during the COVID-19 episode. LDH: Lactate dehydrogenase. CRP: C- reactive protein. IL-6: interleukin-6. ICU: Intensive Care Unit.

Variable		Relapse (n=9)	Non-relapse (n=43)	p	Missing
Age		53 (35-60)	46 (40-57)	0.755	0
Gender (female)		44.4% (4)	76.7% (32)	0.052	0
Charlson Index		2 (0-6)	2 (0-3)	0.562	0
Drug	Rituximab	77.8% (7)	76.7% (33)	1.000	0
	Ocrelizumab	22.2% (2)	23.2% (10)		
	Obinutuzumab	0	0		
Indication	Hematological Malignancy	11.1% (1)	16.3% (7)	0.840	0
	Neurological	44.4% (4)	34.9% (15)		
	Systemic	33.3% (3)	41.9% (18)		
	Hematological	11.1% (1)	6.9% (3)		
Group*	< 6 months	22.0% (9)	78.0% (32)	0.047	0
	> 6 months	0	100% (11)		
Post COVID antiCD20 dose		44.4% (4)	48.8% (20)	0.909	5
Chronic corticosteroids		22.2% (2)	31.7% (13)	0.705	0
Other immunosuppressant		0	22.0% (9)	0.183	0
Persistent positive RT-PCR		37.8% (3)	27.3% (3)	0.600	34
Serum antibody detection		0	33.3% (6)	0.004	27
Cough		77.8% (7)	69.0% (29)	0.704	1
Fever		100% (9)	59.5% (25)	0.021	1
Asthenia		77.8% (7)	53.8% (21)	0.077	6
Arthromyalgia		33.3% (3)	40.0% (16)	1.000	5
Dyspnea		77.8% (7)	23.8% (10)	0.019	2
Pulmonary infiltrate		77.8% (7)	64.3% (18)	1.000	15
Acute corticoid treatment		77.8% (7)	35.7% (15)	0.024	1

**Percentages in this variable are calculated across rows. For the rest of variables, percentages are calculated across columns.

Table 4: Risk factors for relapses during the first episode of SARS-CoV-2 infection. Chronic corticoid was defined as a systemic chronic therapy with corticoids at least with 5mg/kg of prednisone or equivalent at time of SARS-CoV2 infection RT-PCR: reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction

Patient	Recurrence classification	Demographic	AntiCD20	Group	Nº	Time to relapses	Status between episodes	Clinical presentation	Diagnoses	Management	Outcomes
1	Relapse	35 years old women No comorbidity	Multiple sclerosis Ocrelizumab	3-6 Mo. 164 days	2	38 days 112 days	Dyspnea of moderate exertion	Fever, dyspnea, cough Worsening and new pulmonary infiltrates	Nasopharyngeal RT-PCR (Ct unknown)	Corticoid	Radiological improvement. Persistent dyspnea
2	Relapse	56 years old male No comorbidity	High-grade lymphoma Rituximab	< 3 Mo. 33 days	6	34 days 143 days	Asymptomatic	Fever, dyspnea, cough New pulmonary infiltrates Superinfection	Pulmonary biopsy and BAL RT-PCR (Ct 22)	Corticoid, hyperimmune plasm, remdesivir	Since plasm and remdesivir, asymptomatic and radiological resolution
3	Relapse	24 years old women DM	Multiple sclerosis Rituximab	3-6 Mo. 135 days	5	58 days 287 days	Asymptomatic	Fever Worsening and new pulmonary infiltrates	BAL RT-PCR (Ct 23)	Corticoid	Continues with migratory infiltrates. Asymptomatic
4	Possible relapse	35 years old male No comorbidity	Hemolytic anemia Rituximab	3-6 Mo. 154 days	1	51 days	Asymptomatic	Fever, dyspnea, cough New pulmonary infiltrates	No confirmation (no test done)	No specific treatment	Radiological resolution Asymptomatic
5	Relapse	55 years old male CF	Multiple sclerosis Ocrelizumab	< 3 Mo. 65 days	1	36 days	Dyspnea of moderate exertion	Fever, dyspnea, cough Worsening of pulmonary infiltrates	Nasopharyngeal RT-PCR (Ct 29)	No specific treatment	Radiological improvement. Persistent dyspnea
6	Possible relapse	53 years old male No comorbidity	Multiple sclerosis Rituximab	< 3 Mo. 10 days	1	105 days	Asymptomatic	Dyspnea Worsening and new pulmonary infiltrates	Nasopharyngeal RT-PCR (Ct 21)	Corticoid, immunoglobulin	Asymptomatic No radiological follow-up
7	Relapse	48 years old women No comorbidity	Rheumatoid arthritis Rituximab	< 3 Mo. 7 days	3	47 days 83 days	Asymptomatic	Fever, dyspnea, cough New pulmonary infiltrates	BAL RT-PCR (Ct 34)	Corticoid, hyperimmune plasm, immunoglobulin	Asymptomatic No radiological follow-up
8	Relapse	60 years old male	Sjogren's syndrome Rituximab	<3 Mo. 86 days	1	54 days	Dyspnea of moderate exertion	Fever, dyspnea, cough,	BAL RT-PCR (Ct 23)	Corticoid, remdesivir,	Radiological improvement. Asymptomatic

		Liver cirrhosis, CF, CRF						New pulmonary infiltrates Acute respiratory distress		hyperimmune plasm, tocilizumab	
9	Possible relapse	80 years old women HT, DM, CRF	Vasculitis Rituximab	3-6 Mo. 95 days	1	51 days	Asymptomatic	Fever, dyspnea, cough New pulmonary infiltrates Thromboembolism	Nasopharyngeal RT-PCR (Ct 35)	Corticoid	Asymptomatic No radiological follow-up

Table 5: Individual characteristics of patients experiencing a relapse episode after a SARS-CoV-2 infection. DM: Diabetes Mellitus. CF: Cardiac Failure. CRF: Chronic Renal Failure. Mo.; months BAL: Bronchoalveolar lavage. RT-PCR: reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction. Ct: Cycle threshold.